

Bipolar Disorder As An Inborn Phenomenon; An Insight Through The Lens Of Parents

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Abstract

Bipolar disorder (BD) is categorized under mood disorder in DSM-5 TR which is characterized by manic-depressive episodes. It can be hypothesized that it is a disorder developed by birth and remains dormant until any event triggers it and manifests noticeably. Understanding early manifestation can help in timely identification and management. A qualitative study using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) was utilized to understand the developmental patterns of BD by interviewing parents of patients suffering from BP-I and BP-II disorder¹ with and without family history. The results highlighted that home environment, stressful life events, traumatic life events, childhood neglect, parental discord, high expectations, and personality traits predispose the risk population towards the development of BD who has a family history of psychiatric illnesses. The onset of BD is exhibited in late teens with a sudden onset. Spiritual Beliefs tend to be rigid among BD patients and are used as a coping mechanism. Marital life is negatively impacted by BD leading to a high rate of divorce. Stigmatization is a common phenomenon that deleteriously impacts family members' and patients' quality of life. The best treatment option was found to be a combination of medication and psychotherapy.

Keywords: Bipolar Disorder, Developmental Patterns, Parents of Bipolar Patients, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.

Introduction

The war against psychological morbidities doesn't end with the management of symptomologies and goes beyond that. Without finding the solution and associated causal factors we cannot work on prevention; as a Dutch philosopher, Erasmus said "prevention is better than cure" (Murray & Lopez, 1996). The results of research carried out in 2017, the prevalence rate of individuals suffering from bipolar disorder (BD) varies across the world; and this variance accounts for a percentage of 0.3 to 1.2 by country (Dattani et al., 2021). The current study explored the significant aspect of the nature and contributory factors towards the development of BD, early indications and related findings towards effective intervention programs. The journey begins with understanding bipolar disorder's etiology based on the nurture versus nature controversy and develops a hypothesis about its true characteristics.

Mood is characterized as a spectrum of emotions that changes over time and is comprised of fluctuating emotional expressions. This expression may be a single episodic form or persist over time. A broader definition of mood comprises it as a spectrum including a range of emotional expressions which are described as happiness and sadness. When mood fluctuates

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between two extremes, specifically a heightened state known as elation leading towards mania, and a contrasting low state termed as depression or melancholia; this condition is diagnosed as bipolar disorder (BD). Sometimes, these extremities are expressed as co-existing states having conflicting emotions and expressions which may manifest as having feelings of euphoria with chronic irritability (Mason et al., 2016).

Retrospective studies conducted on disorders in children and bipolar disorders among adults help in understanding the early expression of the evolution of BD. A study collected data from support group members. The results suggested that early manifestation involved: low mood, hyperactive behavior and suicidal ideation, before being diagnosed with a manic episode within a BD. Only seventeen percent of the participants reported these symptoms before the age of ten years, and thirty-one percent reported experiencing the symptoms before the age of fifteen years (Lish et al., 1994). According to another study, that collected data from individuals who had their first psychotic episode; sixty-seven percent of patients having BD reported having mental health issues beginning in early childhood, suggesting an early onset and twenty-one percent of the participants reported disruptive behavioral problems (Carlson et al., 2000).

Theoretical Framework

In 1977, Engel proposed the biopsychosocial model that suggests the significant influence of biological, psychological and social factors towards the development of illness and understanding of the concept of health. The interplay of these factors, interacting and influencing each other is vital to the holistic understanding of health conditions.

Figure 1. Visual illustration of theoretical model

The framework of the current study has also been designed on basis of this model highlighting the interaction of nature and nurture's unique interplay.

Literature Review

Chang et al. (2003) analyzed the literature based on studies examining children of parents suffering from BD. The findings demonstrated a significant association of melatonin suppression as children suffering from BD have significantly higher suppression of melatonin levels when exposed to conditions with bright light compared to healthy controls. The results also revealed that children of both parents suffering from BD had marked levels of melatonin suppression as compared to children having one parent suffering from BD and matched

controls. The statistics showed that fifty-seven percent of children having both parents suffering from BD, thirty-three percent of offspring with one bipolar parent and only twenty-one percent of controls showed significant melatonin suppression. It has been concluded that there is a relationship between the degree of melatonin suppression and genetic loading for BD (Nurnberger et al., 1988), as ninety-one percent of adults sample with BD reported to have marked melatonin suppression (Lewy et al., 1985). DelBello et al. (2000) studied neuroanatomic structures in children having a higher risk for BD. The results suggested that the abnormalities found in the adults suffering from BD are similar to those present in children at risk for BD (having one parent diagnosed with BD). This indicates presence of the abnormalities in brain structures even before the onset of BD. In 2003, Chang et al. studied the physiological changes in BD through the use of magnetic resonance spectroscopy. The results suggested a decrease in N-acetyl aspartate (NAA)/creatine ratios in the right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex of bipolar children. The volumetric magnetic resonance imaging exhibited that these patients have changes in their prefrontal, temporal, cerebellar, ventricular, and deeper structural including striatum and amygdala in the context of volume along with white matter abnormalities (Strakowski et al., 2000; 2002). Alloy, et al. (2017) researched circadian rhythm dysregulation in BD. The findings suggested relative circadian phase delay (e.g., later melatonin peak, evening chronotype) is associated with BD, particularly in the depressive phase. More consistent evidence supports irregularity of social rhythms, sleep/wake and activity patterns, and disruptions of social rhythms by life events, as stable trait markers of BD and potential vulnerabilities for the onset of BD. The emerging research reviews a model of an integrative reward system and the involvement of circadian rhythm.

This review provides a solid ground that BD has biological roots emerging from childhood which was explored in the current study.

Methodology

The qualitative research design was utilized for the in-depth exploration of bipolar disorder's developmental trajectory through the lens of parents who have bipolar offspring.

Data Source

A sample of parents of patients (BD-I) with a history of Bipolar disorder in the family (N= 4; mother, n= 2, father, n= 2); Parents of patients (BD-I) with no history of Bipolar disorder in the family (N= 4; mother, n= 2, father, n= 2); Parents of patients (BD-II) with history of Bipolar disorder in the family (N= 4; mother, n= 2, father, n= 2); Parents of patients (BD-II) with no history of Bipolar disorder in the family (N= 4; mother, n= 2, father, n= 2) were interviewed for this purpose using snowball and purposive sampling. The participants (aged 40-65 years) were screened using a mini-mental status examination to rule out neurological conditions and the production of accurate information. The interview protocol was designed using previous research, theories, literature review and the scope of the current study.

Table 1 Demographic Variables of Parents of patients having BP-I disorder

Participant no.	Participant s (Patients with History in the family)	Gender	Age	Socioeconomic Status	Occupation	MMS Score
1	Parent 1	Male	55 years	Middle Class	Laborer	23
2	Parent 2	Male	40 years	Middle Class	Office Job	30

3	Parent 3	Female	50 years	Middle Class	Housewife	30
4	Parent 4	Female	45 years	Middle Class	Housewife	28
	Participants (Patients without History in the family)	Gender	Age	Socioeconomic Status	Occupation	MMS E Score
5	Parent 1	Male	42 years	Middle Class	Office Job	30
6	Parent 2	Male	44 years	Middle Class	Own Shop	31
7	Parent 3	Female	50 years	Middle Class	Housewife	29
8	Parent 4	Female	55 years	Middle Class	Housewife	32

*Socioeconomic status based on assets and income

Table 2

Demographic Variables of Parents of patients having BP-II disorder

Participant no.	Participants (Patients with History in the family)	Gender	Age	Socioeconomic Status	Occupation	MMSE Score
9	Parent 1	Male	50 years	Middle Class	Bank Job	27
10	Parent 2	Male	48 years	Middle Class	Office Job	31
11	Parent 3	Female	59 years	Middle Class	Housewife	30
12	Parent 4	Female	42 years	Middle Class	Housewife	29
	Participants (Patients without History in the family)	Gender	Age	Socioeconomic Status	Occupation	MMSE Score
13	Parent 1	Male	47 years	Middle Class	Office Job	29
14	Parent 2	Male	46 years	Lower Class	Office Job	32
15	Parent 3	Female	52 years	Middle Class	Housewife	28
16	Parent 4	Female	57 years	Middle Class	Housewife	30

*Socioeconomic status based on assets and income

Analysis

IPA was carried out in seven steps including reading and familiarization, initial noting, developing emergent themes, coding, clustering, iteration and narration (Tomkins, 2017).

Results and Discussion

The data was carefully analyzed after transcription using NVIVO-14 into three stages open coding, subordinate themes and superordinate themes along with memo writing.

The results extracted ten main themes discussed below:

Table 3 Main Themes and Sub-themes of Emergence of Bipolar Disorder

Main Theme	Sub-themes
Precipitating Factors	Traumatic Events Negative Life Experiences Life Stressors Adjustment Difficulties Sudden Onset
Onset of illness	Teenage Up to thirty-eight years
Patient's related factors	Personality factors Spiritual Beliefs Vocational Activities Behavioral Disturbances Emotional Expression Stigmatization Coping
Symptoms of Bipolar Disorder	Mania Hypomania Depression Aggression
Marriage	Difficulties in Marriage Separation & Divorce
Predisposing Factors	Genetic History Personality Traits Negative Life Experiences Poor Coping
Family related factors	Role of Parents & Siblings Family Response to Patient's Illness Home Environment Economic Factors Family Concerns Social Factors
Treatment	Role of Medication Treatment Delay Treatment Response Treatment Alternatives
Pattern of illness	Intensity & Duration of Symptoms Perpetuating Factors Prognostic Features Relapse Prevention: Counseling & Continued Medication
Cultural Factors	Cultural Norms

 Stigmatization

Theme 1: Precipitating Factors

In this theme, the main triggers discussed included adjustment issues including home environment, any change in home environment or parental conflict. Alloy et al. (2005) researched the psychosocial context of BD: environmental, cognitive, and developmental risk factors. Findings highlighted that parenting practice comprised of overly protective parenting, lack of care, poor attachment style and relation, and childhood abuse have been commonly found in patients having BD. These factors can further contribute to worsening the course of BD.

Ellicott et al. (1990) established that life stress, in the form of negative life experiences previously linked to the emergence of unipolar depression, was also important for the progression of BD.

Another precipitating factor identified in the current study was difficulty in attaining job, losses in family business, and adjusting to new conditions. Duffy (2010) studied the early stages of BD development. The findings revealed that initial psychopathological manifestations in high-risk individuals for the onset of BD included the presence of anxiety disorders, minor mood disorders and adjustment disorders. These findings underscore the relationship between adjustment challenges during job transitions or adaptation to new environment.

The findings suggest that BD present with a sudden onset with no pre-existing symptoms making it difficult to recognize by family or relatives. Skjelstad, Malt, and Holte (2010) researched symptoms and signs of the initial prodrome of BD using a systematic review. The results indicated that not every person who develops BD experience early symptoms of illness. The present data shows that the mean duration of early symptoms exhibited before a full-blown episode of BD is contradictory but usually ranges from 1.8 to 7.3 years. The most commonly exhibited symptoms of the prodromal stage include irritability and aggression sleep disturbances, depressive states, symptoms related to mania including hyperactivity, anxiety, mood swings and signs of the distal prodrome of BD.

Participant no 3 reported, this issue, “if I recognized symptoms a bit earlier, actually, we have shifted our house”.

Theme 2: Onset of illness

This superordinate theme included the age of onset to be primarily teenage ranging from 17-26 years up to 38 years. The onset usually appears to be sudden with no prodromal symptoms. The second episode intensifies in severity of symptomologies comprised of cycling between mania and depression. The first episode is usually less severe where patients have been found to experience hypomania as well.

Schürhoff and colleagues (2000) studied the early and late onset of BD and found that the early-onset group had the most severe form of BD with more psychotic features and mixed episodes, highly comorbid with panic disorder and poorer prophylactic response to lithium. The first-degree relatives of patients with early onset had a higher risk of developing affective disorders and exhibiting a more severe form of BD. Furthermore, it is suggested that early and late-onset BD differ in clinical expression and familial risk and may therefore be considered to be different sub-forms of manic-depressive illness. The results of this study were consistent with current findings.

According to DSM5-TR the peak age of onset of bipolar I disorder across studies is between 20 and 30 years, but onset occurs throughout the life cycle. Bipolar II disorder can begin in late adolescence and throughout adulthood, the average age at onset is the mid-20s, which is slightly later than for bipolar I disorder but earlier than for major depressive disorder (American Psychiatric Association, 2022).

Nowrouzi and colleagues (2016) suggested that there are two peaks in the age of onset: 15-24 years and 45-54 years, with more than 70% of individuals manifesting clinical characteristics of the condition before 25 years of age.

Participant no 4 reported, "I think she's been depressed since her teenage years, because she was depressed at that time."

Theme 3: Patient related factors

This theme extracted personality factors, spiritual beliefs, vocational activities, behavioral disturbances, emotional expression, stigmatization and coping by patients suffering from BD explained by parents being the caregivers.

Personality factors included traits of attention seeking and sympathy gains by the patients of BD. No theoretical background or literature framework supports this notion and it can be considered as a parental bias towards viewing the disorder. It has been found that bipolar patients may suffer from attention deficit behaviors. Research conducted on sustained attention deficit in BD reported that bipolar I patients were impaired in tasks requiring attention shifting, verbal memory and sustained attention (Clark, Iversen & Goodwin, 2002).

Most common spiritual beliefs found among bipolar patients were rigidity, Islamic wazaif, and spending an abnormal amount of time on supplications and prayers. Azorin and colleagues (2013) studied religious involvement with the relevance of BD. The results revealed that bipolar patients experiencing depressive states may have high religious involvement associated with mixed features which can further increase the risk of suicidal behavior, despite the existence of religious affiliation.

Vocational activities include switching jobs, doing fraud at the workplace, abusive behavior with superiors, and losing a job. Patients suffering from BD were found to be inconsistent in work-allied functioning, and unable to maintain work ethics resulting in job termination and unemployment. Michalak and Colleagues (2007) studied the impact of BD on work functioning and found a lack of continuity in work history, job loss, illness management strategies at the workplace, stigma and disclosure, as well as interpersonal problems at the workplace.

Emotional expression exhibited by patients with BD includes feelings of abandonment, low mood, and mood disparity linked with climate change. Crowe and Colleagues (2012) studied the experiences of feeling out of control due to BD. The results highlighted that all participants reported that their lives have been significantly impacted due to BD specifically self-identity. Patient's feelings towards their diagnosis combined with the family's response lead towards a feeling of being out of control. This feeling of losing control comprises anxiousness lack of autonomy and apprehension of being a flawed person. Aktaş, Ayhan, and Karan (2024) found that climate change leads to emotional impact, negative physical impact, interference in daily life activities, affects symptoms, negatively influences recovery and ways of coping among bipolar patients.

Stigmatization plays a pivotal role in worsening the course of disease and leads to poor coping as observed in the current study. Hawke, Parikh, and Michalak (2013) theorized that stigma poses a serious threat to individuals suffering from BD and negatively impacts the well-being of patients, caregivers and their families. Stigmatization was found to be present within families, social contexts, cultural contexts, work environments, educational sector and goes as far as in health sector. This leads to reduced availability of social support, disturbances in the occupational sector, and disturbed functioning of affected patients, leading towards increased symptomologies and reduced quality of life. These findings were consistent with the current study.

Coping utilized by bipolar patients includes rigid spiritual behavior and magic-related activities. Grover and Colleagues (2016) studied the influence of religion and supernatural beliefs on clinical manifestation and treatment practices in patients with BD. The results

revealed that almost half of the participants (patients suffering from BD) had religious and supernatural themes in their lifetime and believed it to be a causal factor for their illness, including God's will and planetary influence. The participants always approached religious and/or supernatural treatment providers before consulting a health practitioner. More than 90% of patients reported belief in God. The results suggest that this is a form of coping to support oneself not otherwise present.

Participant no 3 reported, "There's also suspiciousness, and when he first started, there was a manic element, and he had pressured speech. This means he talked loudly, but now, thanks to God, he's better with medications."

Theme 4: Symptoms of Bipolar Disorder

Bipolar disorder is comprised of symptoms characterizing episodes of depression, mania, and hypomania. Furthermore, sometimes it is accompanied by psychotic features due to the intensity of the illness. The interviews also yielded symptoms manifested earlier before a full-blown episode occurred.

The episode of depression is comprised of isolation, irritability, an inferiority complex, feelings of worthlessness, neglecting self-care, and poor hygiene including not washing one's clothes and not cleaning one's room. In DSM-5 TR, American Psychiatric Association (2022) reports the diagnostic features of a major depressive episode as a period where the patient suffers from depressed mood, lack of interest even in pleasurable activities, difficulty in sleeping, psychomotor agitation or retardation, feeling worthlessness, fatigued, weight loss or gain, inability to concentrate and suicidal ideation for a minimum of two weeks (with a minimum of five symptoms exhibited excluding the phenomenon of bereavement).

The episode of mania as observed in current study comprised of: manipulative liar, visiting shrines, wandering, threatening other people, snubbing, excessive smoking, hyperactivity, being stubborn, feeling that one's perception is significant, pangs of aggression, yelling, being abusive, verbal aggression, reports of beating mother, scolding children, experiencing high ego, self-talk, over talkativeness, suicidal attempts, arguments, being destructive, difficulty in social interaction, lack of control, hyperactivity, fear of losing spouse, guilt of getting married; offering divorce in empathy and guilt, repetitively remembering past memories, experiencing hallucination, irrelevant conversation, complain of husband to police, progressive deterioration over-time, escaping, overspending, stuck on own point of view, trying to burn house, give excessive money to people, beating others, lack of medicine compliance, lack of reality orientation, authoritative behavior, wandering with children, over religious, performing extra prayers, quarreling, speaking emotionally, feeling suicidal due to aggression, increased sexual desire, demand for marriage, unable to sleep, demanding behavior, escape from hospitals, don't follow commands, lack of understanding, unable to think clearly, using excessive make up, buying excessive clothes, experiencing capgras (imposter syndrome) and nihilistic delusion, staying away from home, grandiosity, suspiciousness, pressured speech, lack of insight, apathetic behavior, restlessness, and increased walking which are in line with diagnostic criteria of DSM-5-TR.

Some of the new themes of behaviors emerged in this data included religious rigidity and over-practice, avoiding social interactions, fear, and guilt. This can stem directly from stigmatization and may worsen the course of BD (Hawke, Parikh & Michalak, 2013).

The episode of hypo mania is comprised of: physical aggression, guilt, weeping episodes, self-blame, lack of insight, lack of medical compliance, mood swings, hyperactivity, delusional behavior, talkativeness, loud speech, big planning, demanding, sometimes feeling sad, feeling isolated, suicidal ideation, experiencing symptoms with less intensity, symptoms are in control, argumentative, erotomania, excessive friendships, egoistic behavior, stubborn behavior, dancing, seasonal changes, pressure of speech, and incongruent mood.

It was found that the reported symptoms of mania and hypomania were found to be common and the main difference lay in the intensity of symptoms varied by the out-of-control state in mania and controlled behaviors in hypomania as highlighted by parents of bipolar patients.

The associated psychotic features include: experiencing psychosis, delusions of reference, erotomania, and grandiosity were most commonly reported by parents. In DSM-5 TR, American Psychiatric Association (2022) reports the associated psychotic features including delusions, hallucinations which can be in congruence to mood i.e. the theme of delusions and hallucinations are typical to mania containing grandiosity, paranoia, nihilism, guilt, deserving punishment, and invulnerability; whereas incongruent to mood psychotic features does not involve above-mentioned themes.

Early manifested symptoms of bipolar disorder include: disconnection from reality, sleep disturbances, experiencing hallucination, symptomatic expression with less intensity, wandering away, going to graveyards, irrelevant talk, sadness, irritability, jealousy, doing excessive makeup, wearing sharp colors, stubbornness, and misbehaving with elders and teachers.

Pfennig and Colleagues (2017) conducted a longitudinal study of the early course of BD. The results suggest that anxiety disorders in childhood are common precursors to the development of BD, difficulty in regulating emotions, crying, feeling worried, being hyper-alert, increased sensitivity, somatic complaints, medical problems, experiencing fear, suicidal ideation, excessive guilt, and loss of pleasure. Premorbid personality features include extraversion, novelty seeking, being highly responsive to reinforcements, and being extremely ambitious. Early manifestations are also reported to be linked with sleep disturbances in terms of quality and duration. Early morning awakening, trouble falling asleep, and waking up from sleep during the night have been observed as key features in children who later develop BD in current study.

Participant no 1 reported, "Basically, she has bipolar disorder. Earlier, she was experiencing mania, and now she's in a depressive episode."

Theme 5: Marriage

Patients suffering from BD have difficulty maintaining a healthy, balanced and quality marriage with themes of marital issues. This includes quarrelling, suspiciousness, and delusions of infidelity, breakup and divorce. The supportive role of the husband as a caregiver includes trying to help and provide treatment. Other marital issues include the spouse not allowing the children to meet other parents, and sharing personal information with other family members.

Granek and Colleagues (2016) studied the impact of BD on patients, spouses, and their marital relationships. The results exhibited that BD has a tremendous effect on the marital life of patients and their spouses which leads to instability, high divorce rates, and emotional disturbances.

Participant no 7 reported, "He had a love marriage that didn't work out. He had kids and his spouse didn't let him meet his children that caused his symptoms to intensify"

Theme 6: Predisposing Factors

The following factors that predispose a person to develop BD include: traumatic events, high expectations, genetic factors, childhood experiences, and encountering stressful situations.

Traumatic events comprise being unable to get admission in the army, family conflict, and the death of a family member. High expectations by family members consist of memorizing the Quran, doing well in studies, and attaining good job. Genetic factors include: a family history of illness, a cousin, uncle, and sister suffering from psychiatric illnesses. Childhood experiences consist of: excessive studying, weeping on fewer marks, demanding behavior,

repetitive complaining, stubborn, apathetic behavior, pampered child, misbehavior, complaints from school, hitting one's head on the wall, slapping oneself, brilliant student, sensitive nature and attachment with others. Encountering stressful situations includes: scolding from teachers, excessive responsibilities, stress of business, job stress, job loss in Covid, and breakup with a partner.

Rowland and Marwaha (2018) studied epidemiology and risk factors for BD. The results of the study showed that several risk factors contribute to the development of BD including genetics, and environmental factors. The severity of symptoms is linked with emotional abuse during childhood and cannabis misuse. Furthermore, medical comorbidities like asthma and irritable bowel syndrome are common among BD patients.

Participant no 1 reported, "Unfortunately, the family didn't treat her with the same behavior as they would to another patient suffering from medical illness."

Participant no 2 reported, "Now we understand that she should also receive spiritual treatment. But let's get her out of this situation first. She's so mentally stressed about how to treat her, what to do, and what not to do. There are also significant financial issues."

Theme 7: Family related factors

The themes that emerged on factors related to family influencing a bipolar patient involve: the role of parents and siblings, family response to the patient's illness, home environment, economic factors, family concerns, and social factors.

The role of parents and siblings; and family response to a patient's illness include: convincing family to approach treatment, lack of awareness towards illness, not being supportive of treatment, blaming others for illness, fear, avoiding patient, understanding illness and being supportive, facing mocking and taunting behavior by a patient, stigmatization, supervising medication, admitting the patient to a health care facility when required, dealing with love and care, regular follow-ups on treatment, approaching spiritual healers, counseling, avoiding arguments with patients, and engaging patient's in activities that channelize their energy.

Home environment factors encompass: a stressful home environment due to the patient's illness, quarrels among family members, and low level of support among family impacting family members and leading to depression, disturbed sleep, and medication. Economic factors include expensive treatment, financial crisis, and difficulty managing expenses. Family concerns comprise posed threat by patients and stigmatization. Social factors include disturbances from the neighborhood, negative friendships, and bad impacts from relatives.

Johnson, Cuellar and Gershon (2015) studied the influence of trauma, life events, and social relationships on bipolar depression. The study reported that early childhood adversity, negative life events, lack of social support, highly expressed emotions, and poor family functioning can lead to depressive symptoms within BD development.

Miklowitz (2007) researched the family's role in the course and treatment of BD. The results suggested that episodes of BD are strongly linked with discord in the family, criticism, and conflicts where the family can benefit from family therapy including communication, problem-solving techniques, and emotional and self-regulation skills which will in turn lead to reduction of stress and delaying the onset of manic episodes.

Participant no 4 reported, "Unfortunately, Pakistani parents often lack awareness about these issues. Instead of understanding that their child has a problem and needs support, they simply tell them to see a psychiatrist. They don't understand the need to empathize and support their child."

Theme 8: Treatment

The treatment related factors include the role of medication, treatment delay, and treatment response and treatment alternatives.

Geddes and Miklowitz (2013) explored the treatment of BD. Results of the study discussed that there is very slow progress in medication where antipsychotics remain most effective for acute mania, and lithium in the prevention of relapse. However, there is significant progress in terms of psychotherapy specifically for the management of major depressive episodes. The best treatment remains in combination with medication along with psychotherapy.

Participant no 4 reported, "when we became certain and realized, we made efforts to counsel him ourselves as well because we had dealt with our elder brother before who suffered from same disorder".

Theme 9: Pattern of illness

The pattern of illness involves the intensity and duration of symptoms, perpetuating factors, and prognostic features. Relapse prevention includes counseling and continued medication.

Subramanian, Sarkar, and Kattimani (2017) studied the course of BD and the contributing factors. The results showed that in Asia the course of BD is predominated by manic episodes where depressive episodes and comorbid anxiety disorder are common in BD-II. The risk factors including early onset and higher episodic frequency are linked with bipolar diathesis. Substance use is the most reported comorbid condition; seasonal pattern and poor sleep quality is also linked as a precursor to BD development.

Participant no 1 reported, "Until she feels satisfied in her heart. Meaning, once it starts, it could last a week, a month, or longer."

Theme 10: Cultural Factors

Cultural factors highlighted in the current study include cultural norms and stigmatization. Michalak and Colleagues (2006) studied the quality of life among bipolar patients which was found to affect profoundly the quality of life, education, vocation, financial functioning as well as social and intimate relationships.

Participant no 4 reported, the doctor advised me to get her counseling too but we were conscious of what people would say in our culture.

Conclusion and Implications

Qualitative research was carried out to determine the developmental patterns of BD to understand its early symptoms, development and course, risk factors, role of family, treatment options, stigmatization and cultural aspects. The study aims to contribute to the early detection of BD leading to early intervention and better management towards managing symptomologies and reducing the rate of relapse, which is a common feature of the disorder. Understanding the risk factors, comorbid conditions, and predisposing features leads to prevention among the population at risk as well as increased quality of life among BD patients.

References

1. Aktaş, M. C., Ayhan, C. H., & Karan, E. (2024). The effect of climate crisis on bipolar disorder: A qualitative study about experiences of individuals diagnosed with bipolar disorder. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 00207640241291521.
2. Alloy, L. B., Abramson, L. Y., Urosevic, S., Walshaw, P. D., Nusslock, R., & Neeren, A. M. (2005). The psychosocial context of bipolar disorder: environmental, cognitive, and developmental risk factors. *Clinical psychology review*, 25(8), 1043-1075.
3. Alloy, L. B., Ng, T. H., Titone, M. K., & Boland, E. M. (2017). Circadian rhythm dysregulation in bipolar spectrum disorders. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, 19(4), 1-10.
4. American Psychiatric Association. (2022). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed., text rev.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425787>

5. Azorin, J. M., Kaladjian, A., Fakra, E., Adida, M., Belzeaux, R., Hantouche, E., & Lancrenon, S. (2013). Religious involvement in major depression: Protective or risky behavior? The relevance of bipolar spectrum. *Journal of affective disorders*, 150(3), 753-759.
6. Carlson, G. A., Bromet, E. J., & Sievers, S. (2000). Phenomenology and outcome of subjects with early and adult onset psychotic mania. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 157(2), 213-219.
7. Chang, K., Steiner, H., & Ketter, T. (2003). Studies of offspring of parents with bipolar disorder. In *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part C: Seminars in Medical Genetics* (Vol. 123, No. 1, pp. 26-35). Hoboken: Wiley Subscription Services, Inc., A Wiley Company.
8. Clark, L., Iversen, S. D., & Goodwin, G. M. (2002). Sustained attention deficit in bipolar disorder. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 180(4), 313-319.
9. Crowe, M., Inder, M., Carlyle, D., Wilson, L., Whitehead, L., Panckhurst, A., ... & Joyce, P. (2012). Feeling out of control: a qualitative analysis of the impact of bipolar disorder. *Journal of psychiatric and mental health nursing*, 19(4), 294-302.
10. Dattani, S., Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2021). Mental Health. Our World in Data. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/mental-health>
11. DelBello, M. P., Soutullo, C. A., Ryan, P., Graman, S. M., Zimmerman, M. E., Getz, G. E., & Strakowski, S. M. (2000). MRI analysis of children at risk for bipolar disorder. *Biological Psychiatry*, 47(8), S13.
12. Doherty EF, MacGeorge EL. Perceptions of Supportive Behavior by Young Adults With Bipolar Disorder. *Qualitative Health Research*. 2013;23(3):361-374. doi:10.1177/1049732312468508
13. Duffy, A., Alda, M., Hajek, T., Sherry, S. B., & Grof, P. (2010). Early stages in the development of bipolar disorder. *Journal of affective disorders*, 121(1-2), 127-135.
14. Ellicott, A., Hammen, C., Gitlin, M., Brown, G., & Jamison, K. (2019). Life events and the course of bipolar disorder. In *Bipolar Disorder* (pp. 78-82). Routledge.
15. Engel, G. L. (1977). The need for a new medical model: A challenge for biomedicine. *Science*, 196(4286), 129-136.
16. Geddes, J. R., & Miklowitz, D. J. (2013). Treatment of bipolar disorder. *The lancet*, 381(9878), 1672-1682.
17. Granek, L., Danan, D., Bersudsky, Y., & Osher, Y. (2016). Living with bipolar disorder: the impact on patients, spouses, and their marital relationship. *Bipolar disorders*, 18(2), 192- 199.
18. Grover, S., Hazari, N., Aneja, J., Chakrabarti, S., & Avasthi, A. (2016). Influence of religion and supernatural beliefs on clinical manifestation and treatment practices in patients with bipolar disorder. *Nordic Journal of Psychiatry*, 70(6), 442-449.
19. Hawke, L. D., Parikh, S. V., & Michalak, E. E. (2013). Stigma and bipolar disorder: a review of the literature. *Journal of affective disorders*, 150(2), 181-191.
20. Johnson, S. L., Cuellar, A., & Gershon, A. (2015). The influence of trauma, life events, and social relationships on bipolar depression. *The Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 39(1), 87.
21. Keenan-Miller, D., Peris, T., Axelson, D., Kowatch, R. A., & Miklowitz, D. J. (2012). Family functioning, social impairment, and symptoms among adolescents with bipolar disorder. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 51(10), 1085-1094.
22. Lewy, A. J., Sack, R. L., & Singer, C. M. (1985, January). Melatonin, light and chronobiological disorders. In *Ciba Foundation Symposium 117-Photoperiodism, Melatonin and the Pineal* (pp. 231-252). Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
23. Lish, J. d., Dime-Meenan, S., Whybrow, P. C., Price, R. A., Hirschfeld, R. M. (1994). The National Depressive and Manic-depressive Association (DMDA) survey of bipolar members. *Journal of affective disorders*, 31(4), 281-294.
24. Mason, B. L., Brown, E. S., & Croarkin, P. E. (2016). Historical Underpinnings of Bipolar Disorder. *Diagnostic Criteria. Behavioral Sciences*, 6(3), 14. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs6030014>
25. Michalak, E. E., Yatham, L. N., Kolesar, S., & Lam, R. W. (2006). Bipolar disorder and quality of life: a patient-centered perspective. *Quality of Life Research*, 15, 25-37.

26. Michalak, E. E., Yatham, L. N., Maxwell, V., Hale, S., & Lam, R. W. (2007). The impact of bipolar disorder upon work functioning: a qualitative analysis. *Bipolar Disorders*, 9(1-2), 126-143.
27. Miklowitz, D. J. (2007). The role of the family in the course and treatment of bipolar disorder. *Current directions in psychological science*, 16(4), 192-196.
28. Murray, C. J. L., & Lopez, A. D. (1996). *The global burden of disease: A comprehensive assessment of mortality and disability from diseases, injuries, and risk factors in 1990 and projected to 2020*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
29. Nowrouzi, B., McIntyre, R. S., MacQueen, G., Kennedy, S. H., Kennedy, J. L., Ravindran, A., ... & De Luca, V. (2016). Admixture analysis of age at onset in first episode bipolar disorder. *Journal of affective disorders*, 201, 88-94.
30. Nurnberger Jr, J., Guroff, J. J., Hamovit, J., Berrettini, W., & Gershon, E. (1988). A family study of rapid-cycling bipolar illness. *Journal of affective disorders*, 15(1), 87-91.
31. Pfennig, A., Leopold, K., Ritter, P., Böhme, A., Severus, E., & Bauer, M. (2017). Longitudinal changes in the antecedent and early manifest course of bipolar disorder—A narrative review of prospective studies. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 51(5), 509-523.
32. Rowland, T. A., & Marwaha, S. (2018). Epidemiology and risk factors for bipolar disorder. *Therapeutic advances in psychopharmacology*, 8(9), 251-269.
33. Schürhoff, F., Bellivier, F., Jouvent, R., Mouren-Siméoni, M. C., Bouvard, M., Allilaire, J. F., & Leboyer, M. (2000). Early and late onset bipolar disorders: two different forms of manic-depressive illness?. *Journal of affective disorders*, 58(3), 215-221.
34. Skjelstad, D. V., Malt, U. F., & Holte, A. (2010). Symptoms and signs of the initial prodrome of bipolar disorder: a systematic review. *Journal of affective disorders*, 126(1-2), 1-13.
35. Strakowski, S. M., DelBello, M. P., Zimmerman, M. E., Getz, G. E., Mills, N. P., Ret, J., ... & Adler, C. M. (2002). Ventricular and periventricular structural volumes in first-versus multiple-episode bipolar disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 159(11), 1841-1847.
36. Subramanian, K., Sarkar, S., & Kattimani, S. (2017). Bipolar disorder in Asia: Illness course and contributing factors. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 29, 16-29.
37. Tomkins, L. (2017). Using Interpretative Phenomenological Psychology in Organisational Research with Working Carers. In *Applied Qualitative Research in Psychology* (J. Brooks & N. King Eds.) pp. 86-100. London: Palgrave Macmillan.